

The Impact of Working Capital Management on the Profitability of Dutch Bangla Bank Limited (DBBL): A Comparative Analysis

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ABSTRACT

A financial institution must assess the impact of working capital management on profitability to decide the relative position of earnings over time. In order to identify which time periods are more realistic in terms of profitability and working capital management, this study evaluates Dutch Bangla Bank Limited's (DBBL) working capital management impact on profitability from 2009 to 2014 and 2016 to 2021. A variety of Dutch Bangla Bank Limited (DBBL) annual reports serve as the only main source for the study's secondary data. In this study, contrast return on networking capital, which is considered a dependent variable, quick ratio, return on equity, and return on assets are viewed as independent factors. Data are evaluated using informative statistics: T-test, correlation, and ANOVA Test (Multiple Regression Analysis). Those test results demonstrate that return on equity has no effect and effect is so negligible on the return on net working capital from 2009 to 2014 and from 2016 to 2021, whereas the return on assets has a significant positive impact on net working capital from 2009 to 2014 and from 2016 to 2021. Additionally, the current ratio has no impact on the return on net working capital from 2009 to 2014 but it has a very beneficial impact starting in the years 2016 and 2021. The 2015–2021 phase had more changes in current ratio, return on equity, and return on working capital than the 2014–2014 phase did. The 2009–2014 period saw more strategic and careful working capital management than the 2015–2021 phase.

Keywords: Working Capital, Profitability Return, Equity Return on Assets, The Quick Ratio, Positive Significant Insignificant Fluctuation.

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INTRODUCTION

Commercial banks use the money in ways that progress a countrys economy and boost wealth all around Commercial banks have the ability to boost the development of the countrys resources and create a significant number of jobs opportunity The World Bank began funding the Commercial Bank Restructuring Project (CBRP) in May 1997 in an effort to further strengthen consolidate and stimulate the growth of the banking industry To accelerate the financial sector reform process a strong Banking Reform Committee (BRC) was also created (BB Hierarchy):

We were frequently unable to determine the commercial banks disbursement trends for different financing sources due to the data provided Working capital comes in two different forms: gross and net The expense of managing the many elements that make up the list of current assets is reflected in the gross working capital Net working capital has two financial implications and its reflects the quantity of existing assets that are supported by long-term resources The net balance of current assets shows the amount that the corporation permanently owns even when current assets and liabilities are disposed of in relatively short periods of time The second justification details the companys financial situation (Das: 2003) Effective working capital financing requires the planning and management of current assets and current liabilities in a way that reduces the risk of not being able to satisfy short-term commitments on the one hand and avoids making excessive investments in these assets on the other The fundamental goals of working capital finance are the preservation and enhancement of the companys liquidity and profitability Undoubtedly financing an organizations working capital requires effective planning and management

LITERATURE REVIEW

The banking sector in Bangladesh is now displaying symptoms of excessive liquidity Despite the central bank taking several steps in this direction the majority of banks have not been able to demonstrate appreciable improvements on indicators like capital to risk weighted asset non-performing loans expenditure-income ratio return on asset return on equity liquid asset and excess liquidity (Khatun F 2019) If a company distributes working capital excessively or inadequately it may find it more difficult to achieve its primary objectives However determining how much working capital a specific business entity requires can be difficult But if you want to effectively manage money and lower the risk of loss while achieving profit goals its essential to assess issues and come up with solutions Inadequate working capital investments threaten the companys existence and restrict its growth Exorbitant working capital expenses are also useless Working capital use and allocation will assist in lowering overall expenses (cost of liquidity and cost of non-liquidity) The researcher felt it was important to compare how working capital management influenced Dutch Bangla Bank Limiteds (DBBL) profitability from 2009 to 2014 and from 2016 to 2021 in light of this.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this study is to compare the impact of working capital management on the profitability of Dutch Bangla Bank Limited (DBBL) between the year 2009 to 2014 and the year 2016 to 2021 To achieve the goal the following specific objectives are assigned:

- a) To spot the working capital scenario of the sample banks during the years 2009-2014 and 2015-2021
- b) To assess the major factor which is affecting the management of banks working capital is being researched
- c) To identify the problems of working capital management of the sample banks during the study period
- d) To recommend remedial measures to overcome the problems of the sample banks in Bangladesh

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

Based on overall review and selected literature the following hypothesis are formulated:

- a)
H0: There is no significant difference regarding return on net working capital return on equity current ratio and return based on assets of the selected bank between the year 2009 to 2014 and 2015 to 2021
H1: There is no significant difference regarding return on net working capital return on equity current ratio and return based on assets of the selected bank between the year 2009 to 2014 and 2015 to 2021
- b)
H0: There is no significant correlation of return on net working capital return on equity current ratio and return based on assets of the selected bank between the year 2009 to 2014 and 2015 to 2021
H1: There is significant correlation of return on net working capital return on equity current ratio and return based on assets of the selected bank between the year 2009 to 2014 and 2015 to 2021
- c)
H0: There is no significant impact of return on net working capital on return on equity current ratio and on return based on assets of the selected bank between the year 2009 to 2014 and 2015 to 2021
H1: There is significant impact of return on net working capital on return on equity current ratio and on return based on assets of the selected bank between the year 2009 to 2014 and 2015 to 2021

HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF DUTCH BANGLA BANK LIMITED

Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited (DBBL) is a joint venture private commercial bank in Bangladesh MD Sahabuddin Ahmed the banks chairman and the Dutch company FMO formed the institution It is the largest bank in Bangladesh based on market capital DBBL was established under the Bank Companies Act of 1991 and organized as a public limited company under the Companies Act of 1994 with the primary objective of conducting all forms of banking activity in Bangladesh The DBBL began conducting business formally on June 3 1996 The Bank is listed on the Chittagong Stock Exchange Limited and the Dhaka Stock Exchange Limited respectively.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Assfaw M Abdu (2018) in his article Determinants of the Financial Performance of Private Commercial Banks in Ethiopia: Bank Specific Factors Analysis emphasized the tight connection between return on assets return on equity and net interest margin and management success of a bank In addition he said

that the performance of liquidity management depends on the management of return on assets return on equity net interest margin capital adequacy ratio and asset quality management He thought there was a strong correlation between a banks financial performance and management effectiveness Additionally he showed that a banks ability to make profits will decrease proportionately as its liquidity rises Return on Assets and Net Interest Margin will become less operationally effective The asset quality of the bank is not seen as a major issue in this situation ~claimed that having more money makes it more difficult to handle difficulties In terms of analytical approaches they place particular focus on the evaluations of return on assets return on equity net interest margin and capital adequacy ratio Multiple Linear Regression and Pearson Correlation Coefficient are the methods they use.

Das PC & Noor Md A (2019) showed in their article Impact of Credit Risk Management on Financial Performance: Panel Evidence from State-Owned and Private Commercial Banks in Bangladesh that there is a strong connection between the three indicators -- return on assets capital adequacy ratio and non-performing loans Because the capital adequacy ratio and the performance of working capital are correlated return on assets and working capital are closely tied They came to the conclusion that when evaluating the financial performance of banks credit risk is an important and key predictor.

Lalon M M (2015) observed in his article Credit Risk Management (CRM) Practices in Commercial Banks of Bangladesh: A Study on Basic Bank Ltd Risks are substantial when financial or banking firms use their default consumers He utilized multiple regression analysis and trend analysis two statistical methods for figuring out the numerous relationships among different variables In order to assess applicants financial performance he used general loan offers the credit teams assessment of their capital ability and collateral He conducted a study to comprehend the value of credit risk management for financial systems He employed a variety of metrics to determine the risks including the current ratio return on equity debt equity ratio and return on assets ratio.

Olaoye F Adekanbi J and Oluwadare O (2019) in their article Working Capital Management and Firms Profitability: Evidence from Quoted Firms on the Nigerian Stock Exchange revealed that risk management has a significant influence on a business companys profitability and that working capital management has a direct impact on risk and profitability of a business organization.

Paul S C Baser A A & Islam M R (2015) showed in their article Liquidity position of private commercial banks (PCBs) in Bangladesh: An Empirical Overview that which can be quickly converted into cash is said to be a liquid asset Due of their ease of acquisition investors place a high value on liquid claims They rely on secondary information that was collected from a number of yearly reports of the institutions that were chosen Ratios such liquid assets to demand liabilities gross loans to total deposits and core deposits to total funding were used They evaluate the hypotheses using ANOVA They found that for the chosen time period the liquidity levels of the selected private commercial banks were fairly high and that having too much liquidity had an effect on the growth of private sector lending.

Raheman and Nasr (2007) performed research on 94 KSE-listed firms between 1999 and 2004 throughout a six-year period Ratios including net operational profitability debt ratio current assets to total assets ratio cash conversion cycle average collection time inventory turnover average payment period current ratio and natural logarithm of sales were employed by the researchers to get to their conclusions Their findings indicated a conflict between effective working capital management and profitability.

Sarker S K (2019) opined in his article A Comparative Analysis on Non-Performing Loans (NPLs) in the Banking Sectors of Bangladesh All banking categories in Bangladesh had different levels of non-performing loans non-performing loans as a percentage of total loans and trends in net non-performing loans as a percentage of total loans He used the Test of Homogeneity Variances and ANOVA to get the findings He emphasized that all of the banking categories fall short of satisfying the universal standards and that there is no equality between them in terms of the homogeneity of variances The ratio of non-performing loans to total loans at the time of his study was 2% In order to promote solid banking operations he advised the banks to monitor frequently and boost operational effectiveness.

Shabnaz A S & Islam A M (2014) described in their article Impact of Working Capital Management on Firms Profitability: Evidence from the Fuel and Power Companies Listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange the profitability of that corporation is significantly impacted by the working Capital Management The time interest ratio (TIE) quick ratio (QR) cash conversion cycle (CCC) accounts receivables collection period (ARCP) accounts payable payment period (APP) inventory processing period (IPP) cash to current liability (CCL) cash to sales (CTS) net working capital turnover (NWC) and debt to equity ratio (D/E) were all taken into consideration when calculating working capital efficiency They also used return on assets (ROA) and net profit margin (NPM) to assess how profitable firms were A correlation matrix and multiple regression were used to evaluate the hypotheses They found that the dependent variable and a few selected independent variables had a noticeable link They concluded that internal regulation market condition and implementation of regulation given by the authority greatly depend on liquidity management.

Shah Md Al E S & Saha A (2011) revealed in their article Performance Indicators of Banking Sector in Bangladesh: A Comparative Study Bangladeshs economic development is greatly influenced by all commercial banks including national commercial banks private commercial banks foreign commercial banks and specialized commercial banks Profitability productivity and SWOT analysis were used to emphasize the performance indicators of banking activities They found that there are substantial differences in interest rates recovery rates the proportion of advances that are not fully repaid cost of funds profitability productivity earning rates etc Additionally their data demonstrated that the selected banks had rising tendencies in a certain dimension even when the overall growth was down They came to the conclusion that effectively employing bank funds would help them to address the problem.

Sultana A (2021) showed in her article Working capital management and its impact on profitability in Sonali Bank Ltd Bangladesh the short-term or current assets that a business organization needs operational money to finance are marketable securities debtors and inventories Profitability is impacted by how quickly existing assets are rotated and converted into cash She obtained the facts from secondary sources She settled on a five-year period In order to evaluate the data find variance using the mean and standard deviation and test hypotheses she used correlation and regression analysis She found that return on equity is positively correlated with debtors collection duration and negatively correlated with working capital and cash conversion cycle She discovered a connection between working capital management and profitability.

Vincent O O & Kusa B Gemechu (2013) found in their article Determinants of Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Kenya The financial management of commercial banks in Kenya is governed by the choices taken by the board and management They used a linear multiple regression model and a modified least squares model to determine the parameters They found that at a 5% level the effects of macroeconomic issues were noticeable They demonstrated a positive correlation between the banks performance enough capital and management effectiveness but a negative correlation for asset quality.

Yahaya A (2015) showed in his article Working Capital Management and Financial Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria that the operational capital of every business is its main support and vitality Examining the effects of working capital management in Nigerian deposit money institutions was his main objective He applied the current ratio quick ratio and cash ratio to evaluate the effect of working capital management He also used return on assets He used correlation and ANOVA to test whether or not the relationship is successful The studys findings showed a strong relationship between return on assets quick ratio and current ratio He showed that the independent variables fast ratio and current ratio have positive correlations whereas there is a negative correlation for the cash ratio All of the variables were significant at the 1% and 5% levels with the exception of company size (the control variable) He arrived to the conclusion that there is a close connection between profitability and liquidity He recommended management to concentrate more on their liquidity in order to maintain the correct balance between liquidity and profitability.

Yahaya A& Bala H(2015) observed in their article Working Capital Management and Financial Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria that the working capital management is regarded as the essential part of a firm.

CONCEPT OF WORKING CAPITAL

Prof Kuchhal S C (1988) opined that ‘The idea of net working capital is a perspective on the management of current assets over the long term that is flexible and controllable yet consistent in short-term analysis and decision-making.

According to **Weygandt et al (2013-2014)** net working capital is the difference between current assets and current liabilities The amount spent on current assets utilized in business operations is known as gross working capital When managing current assets which are consistent in short-term analysis and decision-making but variable and manageable in the long-term the concept of net working capital offers a long-term view.

According to **Pandey I M (2006)** working capital is short-term capital by definition since it primarily meets the short-term financial demands of a business operation This capital is often not kept for more than a year The amount invested in it is circulating or floating since the investment changes in both form and substance as part of regular business operations as opposed to being permanently banned like fixed capital.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Sample of the Study: Dutch Bangla Bank Bangladesh Limited

Variables: The Return on net working capital return on equity current ratio and return on assets are taken as variables of the study.

Periods of the study: The period of the study covers 12 years in two Phases: 1) from 2009 to 2014 and 2) from 2016 to 2021.

Source of Data: The study is covered based on secondary data which has been collected from the annual reports of Dutch Bangla Bank.

Data Analysis: Excel Sheet 2010 is used to determine the mean standard deviation coefficient of variation exponential growth rate minimum and maximum ratio and other variables for comparison between the two phases of the chosen years The size scope and purpose of the study all influence the number of statistical tests that are utilized Testing comes in two flavors: analytical and descriptive Using SPSS software 2014 T-tests (ANOVA-single factor) correlation and multiple regression are performed to analyze the data A 5% level of significance is utilized.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Limitation of the study: The study generally based on limited number of years from 2009 to 2014 and 2015 to 2021 and the source of data is only one source the annual reports of Dutch Bangla Bank Limited Inflation is ignored.

DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

10.1 Analysis of Selected Ratios for the comparison of efficiency of Working Capital Management.

year	Current ratio	Return on equity	Return on working Capital	Return on assets	year	Current ratio	Return on equity	Return on working Capital	Return on assets
2009	170	023	004	001	2016	137	010	003	001
2010	163	025	005	002	2017	133	013	004	001
2011	166	024	005	002	2018	132	018	006	001
2012	168	021	004	001	2019	126	016	007	001
2013	160	016	004	001	2020	108	017	022	001
2014	147	015	004	001	2021	108	015	020	001
Mean	163	021	004	001	Mean	124	015	010	001
SD	008	004	001	000	SD	013	003	009	000
CV	005	020	019	023	CV	010	020	083	022
EGR	007	013	010	010	EGR	003	008	005	009
Max	170	025	005	002	Max	137	018	022	001
Min	147	015	004	001	Min	108	010	003	001

Source: Different annual report of Dutch Bangla Bank and compiled by the researcher

Table 10.1 reveals that the mean of current ratio during the year 2009 -2014 is greater than that of 2015-2021 by $(163-108) = 055$ The table also depicts that the mean of return on equity was greater by $(021-015) = 006$ during the phase 2009-2014 than the phase 2015-2021 But return on working capital is less than $(010-004) = 006$ during the phases 2009-2014 than the phase 2015-2021 There is no difference of the variable 'return on assets' during both phases of selected period of the selected banks In respect of fluctuation of coefficient of variation of current ratio greater fluctuation was observed in the phase 2015-2021 than the phase 2009-2014 by $(010-005) = 005$ In respect of return on equity variation was not observed and in respect of return on net working capital variation was greater in the phase 2015-2021 than the phase 2009-2014 by $(083-019) = 064$ in respect of exponential growth rate of current ratio

return on equity return on net working capital the phase 2009-2014 was better and return on assets was higher by 001 during the phase 2009-2014 than the phase 2015-2021.

Findings from the table 10.1: In respect of mean of current ratio it has been found that liquidity position of the bank was more favorable during the year 2009-2014 than the year 2015-2021 and regarding the issue of mean of return on equity it has been observed that the bank has enough return for the investors during the phase 2015- 2021 than the phase 2009-2014 It has been revealed concerning return on working capital that less recovery of loans direct expenses and disbursement of loans and advances was greater in the phase 2009-2014 than the phase 2015-2021 Obviously working capital management was not so powerful and strategic in the phase 2015-2021 than the phase 2009-2014 and there is no difference of the variable return on assets' during the selected period of the selected banks In respect of coefficient of variation greater fluctuation of current ratio return on equity and return on working capital was observed.

DATA INTERPRETATION

Hypothesis (a)

H₀: There is no significant difference regarding return on net working capital return on equity current ratio and return on assets of the selected bank between the year 2009 to 2014 and 2015 to 2021.

H₁: There is no significant difference regarding return on net working capital return on equity current ratio and return on assets of the selected bank between the year 2009 to 2014 and 2015 to 2021.

Table No: 11.1 T-Test on Return on Net Working Capital

	Time limit	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Std Error Mean
Return on Net Working Capital	2009-2014	6	00433	000516	000211
	2016-2021	6	01033	008406	003432

Table No: 11.2

		Levene's Test of equality of variances		T-test for equality of means				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig	t	df	sig(2 tailed)	Mean Difference	lower	Upper
RoNWC	Equal Variance Assumed	1274	0322	20555	5	0000	006	00379	00488
	Equal Variance not Assumed			3011	5	0030	006	00151	01916

Interpretation of the table 11.1 and 11.2: Mean values of Return on Working Capital of the year 2009-2014 are 00433 and the year 2016- 2021 is 01033 Mean difference is 006 the value of t is 20055 and it is significant (p value<005) at 5% level That means there is a significant difference between the net working capital of the year 2009-2014 and 2016-2021 Here the return on net working capital of the year 2009-2014 is significantly lower than that of the year 2016-2021.

Table No: 11.3 T-Test on Return on Equity

	Time limit	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Std Error Mean
Return on Equity	2009-2014	6	02067	004227	001726
	2016-2021	6	01483	002927	001195

Table No: 11.4

		Levene's Test of equality of variances		T-test for equality of means				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig	t	df	sig(2 tailed)	Mean Difference	lower	Upper
RoE	Equal Variance Assumed	0000	0000	11976	5	0000	00584	01623	02510
	Equal Variance not Assumed			12414	5	0000	00584	01176	01790

Interpretation of table 11.3&11.4: Mean values of Return on Working Capital of the year 2009-2014 are 02067 and the year 2016-2021 is 01483. Mean difference is 00584. The value of t is 12414 and it is significant (p value < 0.05) at 5% level. That means there is a significant difference between the return on equity of the year 2009-2014 and 2016-2021. Here return on equity of the year 2009-2014 is significantly higher than that of the year 2016-2021.

Table No: 11.5: T- Test on Return on Assets

	Time limit	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Std Error Mean
Return on Assets	2009-2014	6	00133	00516	00211
	2016-2021	6	00100	00000	00000

Table No: 11.6

		Levene's Test of equality of variances		T-test for equality of means				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig	t	df	sig(2 tailed)	Mean Difference	lower	Upper
RoA	Equal Variance Assumed	0000	0000	6325	5	001	00033	0079	0188
	Equal Variance not Assumed			9238137158	5	000	00033	0100	0100

Interpretation of tables 11.5 & 11.6: Mean values of Return on assets of the year 2009-2014 are 00133 and the year 2016-2021 is 00100. Mean difference is 00033. The value of it is 9238137158 and it is

significant (p value < 0.05) at 5% level That means there is a significant difference between the return on assets of the year 2009-2014 and 2016-2021 Here return on assets of the year 2009-2014 is significantly higher than that of the year 2016-2021.

Table No: 11.7: T-Test on Current Ratio

	Time limit	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Std Error Mean
Current Ratio	2009-2014	6	16233	08311	03393
	2016-2021	6	12400	12884	05260

Table No: 11.8

		T-test for equality of means							
		Levene's Test of equality of variances						95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig	t	df	sig(2 tailed)	Mean Difference	lower	Upper
Current Ratio	Equal Variance Assumed	0000	0000	47846	5	000	03833	15361	17105
	Equal Variance not Assumed			23575	5	000	03833	11048	13752

Interpretation of table 11.7 & 11.8: Mean values of current ratio of the year 2009-2014 are 16233 and the year 2016- 2021 is 12400 The mean difference is 03833 the value of t is 23575 and it is significant (p value < 0.05) at 5% level That means there is a significant difference between the current ratio of the year 2009-2014 and 2016-2021 Here the current ratio of the year 2009-2014 is significantly higher than that of the year 2016-2021.

Findings from T-Test:

- Return on net working capital of the year 2009-2014 is significantly lower than that of the year 2016-2021
- Return on equity return on assets and current ratio of the year 2009-2014 is significantly higher than that of the year 2016-2021

Hypothesis (b)

H0: There is no significant correlation of return on net working capital return on equity current ratio and return on assets of the selected bank between the year 2009 to 2014 and 2015 to 2021.

H1: There is significant correlation of return on net working capital return on equity current ratio and return on assets of the selected bank between the year 2009 to 2014 and 2015 to 2021.

Table No: 11.9: Correlation among the variables related to working capital ratio and profitability ratio

		Return on Net working capital	Return on equity	Return on assets	Current Ratio
Return on Net working capital	Pearson Correlation	1	-0125	-0168	-0759**
	Sig (2-tailed)		0700	0602	0004
	N	12	12	12	12
Return on equity	Pearson Correlation	-0125	1	0683*	0625*
	Sig (2-tailed)	0700		0014	0030
	N	12	12	12	12
Return on assets	Pearson Correlation	-0168	0683*	1	0442
	Sig (2-tailed)	0602	0014		0150
	N	12	12	12	12
Current Ratio	Pearson Correlation	-0759**	0625*	0442	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	0004	0030	0150	
	N	12	12	12	12
**Correlation is significant at the 001 level (2-tailed)					
* Correlation is significant at the 005 level (2-tailed)					

Interpretation of the table 11.9: Correlation co-efficient among return on net working capital return on equity and return on assets is -0125 and -0168 and which means it has insignificant negative correlation with return on net working capital (p value>005) but with current ratio correlation co-efficient is 0004(p value>005) meaning it has positive significant correlation with return on net working capital Correlation co-efficient between return on equity and return on assets is 0683 which is significant (p value< 005) at 5% level That means there is a significantly positive correlation between return on equity and return on assets Moreover return on equity has a positive correlation with the current ratio which is 0625 and it is significant at 5% level The current ratio has a significant negative correlation with return on net working capital (-0759) at 1% level and it has also positive correlation with return on asset (065) at 5% level The study found that there is no perfect or nearly perfect correlation among the independent variables So it may be assumed that the variables are free from multi-collinearity effects So it is logical to fit regression model of profitability variable on working capital variable.

Findings from correlation

Return on net working capital has insignificant negative correlation with return on equity and return on assets but with current ratio it has significant negative correlation where the coefficient is -0759 at 5% level indicating one-unit increases in current ratio decreases 0759 unit in return on net working capital A moderate significant and positive correlation exists among return on equity return on assets and current ratio Return on equity has the coefficient of 0683 at 5% level indicating one-unit increase in return on equity causes 0683-unit increase in net working capital Again return on equity has positive significant correlation with current assets (0625 at 5% level).

Hypothesis (c)

H0: There is no significant impact of return on net working capital on return on equity current ratio and on return on assets of the selected bank between the year 2009 to 2014 and 2015 to 2021.

H1: There is significant impact of return on net working capital on return on equity current ratio and on return on assets of the selected bank between the year 2009 to 2014 and 2015 to 2021.

Table 11.10: Multiple Regression Analysis

Model Summary for 2009-2014

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of the Estimate
1	1000(a)	1000	1000	00000
Predictors: (Constant) return on equity return on assets and current ratio				
Dependent variable: Return on net working capital				

Table No11.10: shows the model summary value of multiple correlation coefficients Here R is 1000 for the Measures of networking capital management for the selected commercial bank where the predictor variables return on equity return on assets and current ratio collectively explained 100 percent of the dependent variable return on networking capital Moreover Multiple R-Square Adjusted R-Square and Std Error of the Estimate are found to be 1000 1000 and 0000 respectively indicating quite acceptable result for well fit of model of the undertaken study These indicate that there exists a high degree of linear association between return on net working capital and independent variables.

Table 11.11: Analysis of Variance for 2009-2014

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1	Regression	000	3	000	6261623921829440	000(a)
	Residual	000	2	000		
	Total	000	5			
Predictors: (Constant) return on equity return on assets and current ratio						
Dependent variable: Return on net working capital						

Table 11.11 reveals that the sum of squares due to regression is 0000 and the residual is 0000 Table value of F is 6261623921829440 where degree of freedom (32) is at 5% level Since the calculated value of F (6261623921829440) is greater than the table value of F (005) The hypothesis is rejected at 000 percent level of significance On the basis of this analysis it is found that there exists a significant relationship between the population mean and the sample mean indicating the model is the best fitted for the study period

Table 11.12: Analysis of Regression Coefficients for 2009-2014

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.030	.000		2393257911	.000		
	Return on equity	-.535E-017	.000	.000	.000	1000	.114	8758
	Return on assets	1000	.000	1000	6921515568	.000	.255	3921
	Current Ratio	343E-017	.000	.000	.000	1000	.216	4625
Dependent variable: Return on net working capital								

The Coefficients Measurements of networking capital management for DBBL have been depicted in the above Table 1112 where the dependent variable is return on networking capital and the predictors: (Constant) are return on equity return on assets and current ratio under the study period B value of the table represents the degree to which extent the dependent variable can be affected by a certain independent variable while another independent variable remains constant The β coefficient for return on equity is $-535E-017$ units reveals that the one-unit increment of return on equity causes to decrement of return on net working capital in $535E-017$ units while other independent variables remain constant indicating inverse relationship with one another Here the value of t is insignificant So it can be said that return on equity may not have a negative effect on return on net working capital The β coefficient for return on assets is 1000 units reveals that the one-unit increment of return on assets causes to increment of return on net working capital in 1000 units while other independent variables remain constant The value of t is 6921515568 and it is significant at 5% level So it can be concluded with a 100% confidence level that returns on assets have a positive effect on return on net working capital as the significant value is 0000 The current ratio involves $343E-017$ β_3 value which denotes when current ratio increases one unit return one net working capital also increase by $343E-017$ units while other independent variables remain constant The value of t s 0000 which is statistically significant at 5% level So it can be concluded with 100% confident interval as significant value is 0000 which denotes the probability of rejecting this conclusion is 000% Therefore it can be concluded that the current ratio has a significant positive impact on return on net working capital In the model variance inflationary factors (VIF) were found between 3921 to 8758 indicating expected acceptable extend of multi-collinearity.

Based on the result regression equation can be carved as follows:

$$\text{RONWC} = 0030 - 535E-017 \text{ ROE} + 1000 \text{ ROA} + 343E-017 \text{ CR} + \epsilon$$

Table 11.13: Model Summary for 2016-2021

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of the Estimate
1	988(a)	976	960	01678
Predictors: (Constant) return on equity return on assets and current ratio				
Dependent variable: Return on net working capital				

Table No1113 shows the model summary value of multiple correlation coefficient Here R is 0988 for the Measures of networking capital management for the selected commercial bank where the predictor variables return on equity return on assets and current ratio collectively explained 98 percent of the dependent variable return on networking capital Moreover Multiple R-Square Adjusted R-Square and Std Error of the estimate are found to be 0976 0960 and 01678 respectively indicating quite acceptable result for well fit of model of the undertaken study These indicate that there exists a high degree of linear association between return on net working capital and independent variables

Table 11.14: Analysis of Variance for 2016-2021

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1	Regression	034	2	017	61208	004(a)
	Residual	001	3	000		
	Total	035	5			
Predictors: (Constant) return on equity return on assets and current ratio						
Dependent variable: Return on net working capital						

Table 1114 reveals that the sum of squares due to regression is 0034 and the residual is 0001 The table value of F is 61208 where degree of freedom (23) is at 5% level Since the calculated value of F 61208 is greater than the table value of F The hypothesis is rejected at 000 percent level of significance On the basis of this analysis it is found that there exists a significant relationship between the population mean and the sample mean indicating the model is the best fitted for the study period.

Table 11.15: Analysis of Regression Coefficients for 2016-2021

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	911	109		8332	004	
	Return on equity	-031	291	-011	-107	922	777
	Return on assets	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Current ratio	-648	066	-993	-9804	002	777
Dependent variable: Return on net working capital							

The Coefficients Measurements of networking capital management for DBBL have been depicted in the above Table 1115 where the dependent variable is return on networking capital and the predictors: (Constant) are return on equity return on assets and current ratio under the study period B value of the table represents the degree to which extent the dependent variable can be affected by a certain independent variable while another independent variable remains constant The β coefficient for return on equity is -0011 units reveal that the one-unit increment of return on equity causes to decrement of return on net working capital in -0011 units while other independent variables remain constant indicating inverse relationship with one another Here the value of t is insignificant So it can be said that return on equity may not have a negative effect on return on net working capital The β coefficient for return on assets is 0000 units reveals that the one-unit increment of return on assets causes to equal increment of return on net working capital in 0000 units while other independent variables remain constant The value of t is 0000 and it is significant at 5% level So it can be concluded with a 100% confidence level that returns on assets have positive effect on return on net working capital as the significant value is 0000 The current ratio involves -0993 β 3 value which denotes when current ratio increases one unit return one net working capital also decreases by 0993 units while other independent variables remain constant The value of t -9804 which is statistically significant at 5% level So it can be concluded with 100% confident interval as significant value is 0002 which denotes the probability of rejecting this conclusion is 000% Therefore it can be concluded that the current ratio has a significant positive impact on return on net working capital In the model variance inflationary factors (VIF) were found 1287 indicating expected acceptable extend of multi-collinearity.

Based on the result regression equation can be carved as follows:

$$RONWC = 0911 - 0031 ROE + 0000 ROA - 0468 CR + \epsilon$$

RESULT OF HYPOTHESES TESTING OF THE YEAR 2009-2014

This testing P-value (Significant Level) is denoted 005 Here confidence level of interval is accepted 95% To achieve the confident interval P-value must be equal to or less than 005 Null hypothesis must not be rejected if it exceeds 005 levels.

P- Value of β coefficient of return on equity is 1000 which indicates that the return on equity has no effect on return on net working capital Here the probability of accepting null hypothesis is 100% since the P- value is 1000 which is more than 005 Based on this result H0 can be accepted and H1 is rejected So we may conclude that return on equity has no effect on Net working capital of the year 2009 to 2014 and it is insignificant.

P - Value of β coefficient of return on assets is 0000 which denotes that return on assets affects return on net working capital with 100% confident interval Here the probability of rejecting null hypothesis is 100% since the P - value is 0000 which is less than 005 and it is statistically significant Based on this result H1 can be accepted and H0 is rejected Therefore we may conclude that return on assets has a positive significant effect on return on net working capital of the year 2009 to 2014.

P - Value of β coefficient of current ratio is 1000 which denotes that current ratio has no effect on return on net working capital Here the probability of accepting null hypothesis is 100% since the P - value is 1000 which is more than 005 and it is not significant statistically Based on this result H0 can be accepted and H0 is rejected Therefore we may conclude that the current ratio has no effect on return on net working capital from the year 2009 to 2014.

RESULT OF HYPOTHESES TESTING OF THE YEAR 2016-2021

This testing P-value (Significant Level) is denoted 005 Here confidence level of interval is accepted 95% To achieve the confident interval P-value must be equal to or less than 005 Null hypothesis must not be rejected if it exceeds 005 levels.

P- Value of β coefficient of return on equity is 0922 which indicates that the return on equity effect on return on net working capital with 8% confident interval Here the probability of rejecting null hypothesis is 92% since the P- value is 0610 which is more than 005 Based on this result H1 can be rejected and H0 is accepted So we may conclude that return on equity has no effect on Net working capital of the year 2016 to 2021 and it is also insignificant.

P - Value of β coefficient of return on assets is 0000 which denotes that return on assets affects return on net working capital with 100% confident interval Here the probability of rejecting null hypothesis is 100% since the P - value is 0000 which is less than 005 and it is statistically significant Based on this result H1 can be accepted and H0 is rejected Therefore we may conclude that return on assets has a positive significant effect on return on net working capital of the year 2016 to 2021.

P - Value of β coefficient of current ratio is 0002 which denotes that current ration effect on return on net working capital with 100% confident interval Here the probability of rejecting null hypothesis is 100% since the P - value is 0000 which is less than 005 and it is statistically significant Based on this

result H0 can be accepted and H1 is rejected Therefore we may conclude that the current ratio has a significant positive effect on return on net working capital from the year 2016 to 2021.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

Return on net working capital for the years 2009 to 2014 is significantly lower than for the years 2016 to 2021 even though return on equity return on assets and current ratio are all significantly higher for the years 2009 to 2014 than for the years 2016 to 2021 indicating that both the bank's ability to manage working capital more effectively during the years 2009 to 2014 and the years 2016 to 2021 Positive net working capital also shows good debt repayment advancement and working capital management in both phases of the selected time The 2009-2014 phase had a lower rate of loan recovery direct expenditures and loan and advance disbursement than the 2015-2021 period according to research on return on working capital There was no change in the variable return on assets for the chosen time of the chosen banks and working capital management in the 2015–2021 phase was obviously less strategic or successful than it had been in the 2009–2014 phase In terms of coefficient of variation the current ratio return on equity and return on working capital all fluctuated more.

CONCLUSION

It was discovered that return on equity had an inverse association with return on net working capital throughout the research period because the coefficient for return on equity is $-535E-017$ units and the t value was in 2009-2014 From 2016 through 2021 the return on equity coefficient is -0011 Return on assets again had a strong positive link with return on net working capital since the coefficient for return on assets is 1000 units from 2009 to 2014 and the coefficient for return on equity is -0011 from 2016 to 2021 The current ratio has a large positive impact on return on net working capital The study's conclusions and those from the relevant literature review are all in agreement Therefore it is evident that Dutch Bangla Bank needed to place a greater emphasis on the efficient management of working capital in order to prevent liquidity risk.

RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

To determine the worth of investor speculation the following recommendations can be made: It's crucial to establish working capital guidelines and standards and to inform investors about them Investors will be able to fulfill the requirements and consequently make better financial decisions Both present and potential investors should have access to information on allocated working capital funding so that they may be inspired to contribute to the company's strong financial performance.

Cash investments loans and other items are included in banks' asset portfolios According to an analysis of the institutions' selected techniques for working capital management the current share has been increasing over time The assessment's main objective was working capital management which will assist the company in managing working capital profitably Throughout the entire research period sample banks had excellent liquidity and their assets were sufficient to cover their liabilities This study demonstrates that the overall working capital (WC) of the sample banks has expanded by more than 100% in recent years which is an important trend and offers a strong foundation for the health of the selected bank The overall quantity of net profit fluctuated during the course of the research period which should be reduced Therefore banks should evaluate the borrowers' capacity and willingness to repay the loan before approving it.

The researcher suggests carrying out more research on the same topic in numerous businesses and related areas and prolonging the sample duration.

REFERENCES

- Assfaw M A (2018) Determinants of the Financial Performance of Private Commercial Banks in Ethiopia: Bank Specific Factors Analysis *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: C Finance* 18(3) p 54-67
- Edwards, A. A., Steacy, L. M., Siegelman, N., Rigobon, V. M., Kearns, D. M., Rueckl, J. G., & Assfaw M A (2018) Determinants of the Financial Performance of Private Commercial Banks in Ethiopia: Bank Specific Factors Analysis *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: C Finance* 18(3) p 54-67
- Das PC & Noor Md A (2019) Impact of Credit Risk Management on Financial Performance: Panel Evidence from State-Owned and Private Commercial Banks in Bangladesh *The Cost Management* 47(4) p 22-37
- Khatun F & Saadat SY (2019) Governance and Competitiveness: An econometric Analysis of the Banking Sector of Bangladesh *Journal of Statistical and Econometric Methods* 8(4) P 1-4
- Kuchhal SC (1988) *Financial Management* Chaitanya Publishing House New Delhi India P 155
- Lalon M M (2015) Credit Risk Management (CRM) Practices in Commercial Banks of Bangladesh: A Study on Basic Bank Ltd *International Journal of Economics Finance and Management Sciences* 3(2) p 78-90
- Olaoye F Adekanbi J and Oluwadare O (2019) Working Capital Management and Firms' Profitability: Evidence from Quoted Firms on the Nigerian Stock Exchange *Intelligent Information Management* 1(3) p 43-60
- Pandey IM (1999) *Financial Management* Vikas Publishing House Private Ltd Newdelhi India P 814-815
- Paul S C Baser A A & Islam M R (2015) Liquidity Position of Private Commercial Banks (PCBs) in Bangladesh: An Empirical Overview *The Bangladesh Accountant* P 78-85
- Raheman A & Nasr M (2007) Working Capital Management and Profitability – Case Of Pakistani Firms *International Review of Business Research Papers* 3(1) p 279 – 300
- Sarker S K (2019) A Comparative Analysis on Non-Performing Loans (NPLs) in the Banking Sectors of Bangladesh *International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah* 7(1) p 297-314
- Shah Md E S & Saha A (2011) Performance Indicators of Banking Sector in Bangladesh: A Comparative Study *ASA University Review* 5(1) p 21-36
- Shabnaz A S & Islam A M (2014) Impact of Working Capital Management on Firm's Profitability: Evidence from the Fuel and Power Companies Listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange *Journal of Business Studies* 35(1) p178-199
- Sultana A (2021) Working Capital Management and its Impact on Profitability in Sonali Bank Ltd Bangladesh *IQSR Journal of Economics and Finance* 12(1) p 52-57
- Vincent O O & Kusa B G (2013) Determinants of Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Kenya *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues* 3(1) P 237-252
- Weygandt J J Kimmel P D & Keiso D E (2013-2014) *Accounting Principles* John Willy & Sons USA p 12-14
- Yahaya A (2015) Working Capital Management and Financial Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting* 6(16) p 57-71
- Yahaya A & Bala H (2015) Working Capital Management and Financial Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting* 6(16) p-57-72